

PROS AND CONS OF TEETH WHITENING**Aliyev M.,***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine
Department of Terapeutik Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan***Aliyev T.,***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant
Department of Pediatric Dentistry
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan***Yagubova F.***Department of Pediatric Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7495309>**Abstract**

Subject. Whitening techniques do not exclude the occurrence of undesirable consequences for tooth tissues after the whitening procedure. The study of the effect of a whitening agent on the hard tissues of the teeth and the elimination of complications remains an important and urgent issue. As a result of whitening, not only the discoloration of the organic component of the hard tissues of the teeth occurs, but also its partial death, which is expressed in the expansion of the enamel tubules and the change in the hydrodynamic processes in the tooth enamel.

Keywords: whitening, remineralizing therapy, laser phonophoresis, hard tissue structure.

In modern literature, there are many scientific publications that reflect various clinical and experimental aspects on the effect of whitening systems on the structure of hard tooth tissues. Most modern whitening systems include preparations of hydrogen peroxide or carbamide peroxide in combination with activating factors. Whitening agents are used externally or placed inside the tooth cavity when whitening pulpless teeth. In both cases, the aim is to whiten chromogens inside the dentin, thus changing the basic color of the tooth [3]. The permeability of the enamel of a living tooth is considered as a physiological process that provides the processes of ion exchange, mineralization and remineralization of the enamel [1, 2]. Nowadays, whitening methods do not exclude the occurrence of undesirable consequences for tooth tissues after the whitening procedure. The implementation of the enamel remineralization process is possible due to the properties possessed by hydroxyapatite crystals [7.8.9]. Enamel behaves like a porous membrane and small ions penetrate deeper more easily than large molecules that are adsorbed on the surface and can be desorbed without changing the shape of the crystals [3]. The penetration of substances into the enamel and ion exchange occur in several stages. From the surface of the enamel, through microspaces, ions penetrate into the aqueous layer of the crystal, from there to the surface of the crystal, and only later - from the surface to various sections of the crystal lattice. If the first stage lasts for several minutes, then the third stage lasts for tens of days [1]. Many authors point to the features of the surface layer of enamel, which differs from the deeper layers of enamel in greater mineralization, density, physical resistance, microhardness, resistance to caries [1-4]. As

a result of whitening, not only discoloration of the organic component of the hard tissues of the teeth occurs, but also its partial death, which is expressed in the expansion of the enamel tubules and the change in hydrodynamic processes in the tooth enamel [5.6]. Thus, the study of the effect of a whitening agent on the hard tissues of the teeth and the elimination of complications remains an important and urgent issue.

The purpose of the study was to study the histological changes in enamel and dentin during teeth whitening, as well as their subsequent treatment with remineralizing agents. Materials and methods

For histological examination, 18 intact teeth were selected, removed for orthodontic indications after the in vitro whitening procedure, and 6 intact teeth that were not subjected to the whitening procedure (control group). For teeth whitening, a system was chosen, which included a gel based on 35% hydrogen peroxide. The teeth were fixed in silicone impression material, a whitening gel was applied to the pre-cleaned and dried enamel surface with a layer of 23 mm.

Using a lamp, the bleaching gel was activated for 10 minutes. The bleaching procedure was carried out twice. After the procedure of bleaching and remineralizing therapy, histological preparations were made by washing, dehydrating, fixing in paraffin and making sections using a microtome. After the whitening procedure, the teeth were divided into four groups of 6 teeth each: Group I - intact teeth removed for orthodontic reasons (control group); Group II - intact teeth that have undergone a whitening procedure; Group III - intact teeth after bleaching, treated with a preparation based on zinc-substituted carbonate hydroxyapatite Stomysens (BioRepair); Group IV - intact teeth after whit-

ening and remineralizing therapy (Stomysens (BioRepair)) based on zinc-substituted carbonate hydroxyapatite in combination with laser phonophoresis.

Research results

The study of the histological structure of group I of the studied teeth revealed a compact structure of the enamel, the enamel-dentin border was clear, no structural changes were found in the dentin - the dentinal tubules were not expanded, they were arranged in parallel rows. In group II of the studied teeth, significant morphological changes in the structure of enamel and dentin were revealed - an uneven surface of the enamel was visualized with its partial delamination, as well as the presence of large cavities, the enamel-dentin border was not traced, a large number of large cavities were revealed in the dentin structure. In group III, a small number of morphological changes were noted, there was a small number of small pores in the enamel structure, the enamel-dentin border was clear, a small number of small pores were visualized in the peripulpal dentin, the dentinal tubules were slightly expanded, arranged in parallel rows. Morphological changes were observed in group IV in the structure of the enamel in the form of pores, delamination of the enamel was visualized, the enamel-dentin border was not traced, there were no pathological changes in the dentin, the dentinal tubules were not expanded, they were arranged in parallel rows, the structure of the dentin was compact, identical to the control.

Thus, the study revealed significant structural changes in the enamel and dentin of the teeth resulting from bleaching, manifested in the form of an uneven surface of the enamel with its partial delamination, as well as the presence of large cavities, the enamel-dentin border was not traced, a large number of large cavities. The use of remineralizing agents led to a partial restoration of the structure of enamel and dentin of bleached teeth. The use of Stomysens (BioRepair) based on zinc-substituted carbonate hydroxyapatite as a remineralizing agent led to a significant restoration of the enamel structure and partial restoration of the dentin. Whereas the use of this drug in combination with laser phonophoresis led to complete normalization of the dentin structure, however, the enamel structure remained the same.

Conclusions

Teeth whitening results in significant structural changes in both enamel and dentin. To restore the enamel structure, it is most preferable to use a preparation based on zinc-substituted carbonate hydroxyapatite (Stomysens (BioRepair)). The combined use of

this drug with laser phonophoresis has the greatest effect on dentin.

References:

1. Borovsky E.V., Leontiev V. K *Biologija polosti rta* [Biology of the oral cavity]. Moscow, Medical book, N. Novgorod, Publishing house of the ngma, 2001, 304 p.
2. Gazhva S.I., Zhulev E.N., Progressive D.A., Rostov A.V. [Evaluation of microstructure changes in the topography of the enamel and its microhardness, depending on the influence of different bleaching systems]. *Sovremennye problemy nauki i obrazovanija = Modern problems of science and education*, 2015, no. 2, part 3, pp. 14-20. (In Russ.)
3. Krikheli N.I. *Otbelivanie zubov i mikroabrazija jemali v jesteticheskoj stomatologii. Sovremennye metody* [Teeth whitening and enamel microabrasion in aesthetic dentistry. Modern methods]. Moscow, publishing house of Practical medicine, 2008, pp. 191-204.
4. Uspenskaya O.A., Shevchenko E.A., Kazarina N.In. [Dentistry pregnant Methodical recommendations]. *Zhurnal mikrobiologii, jepi- demiiologii i immunobiologii = Journal of Microbiology, epidemiology and Immunobiology*, 2009, no. 2, pp. 101-103. (In Russ.)
5. Terehova N.V. *Klinicheskaja jeffektivnost' otbelivaniya vital'nyh zubov // Stomatologicheskij zhurnal*. – 2011. – №3. – S.221–224.
6. Hayward R., Osman Y., Grobler S.R. *Aclinical study of the effectiveness of a light emitting diode systems on tooth bleaching // Open Dent J*. – 2012. – №6. – P.143–147.
7. Haywood V.B. *Commonly asked questions about nightguard vital bleaching // Dent-Assist*. – 1996. – Vol.65, N2.
8. Li Y., Greenwall L. *Safety issues of tooth whitening using peroxide-based materials // British Dental Journal*. – 2013. – Vol.2156, N1. – P.29–34.
9. Marshall K., Berry T.G., Woolum J. *Tooth whitening: current status // Compend. Contin. Educ. Dent*. – 2010. – Vol.31, N7. – P.486–492, 494–495.